

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DEMONSTRATIVES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17802211>

Annotation. This article is dedicated to a comparative study of the structure, use, and linguistic functions of demonstrative pronouns in English and Uzbek languages. Demonstrative pronouns act as a vital element in communication to accurately identify a person, things, and places. In English, the demonstrative pronouns "this," "that," "these," and "those" are used, while in Uzbek, the forms "bu," "shu," and "u" are used. The article examines linguistic structures and syntactic structures of both languages and presents the similarities and differences of pronouns. Based on this analysis, common and specific features of both languages were detected, which can be a useful source of knowledge for foreign language learners.

Key words: demonstrative pronouns, English language, Uzbek language, comparative analysis, grammar, syntax.

Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена сравнительному изучению структуры, использования и лингвистических функций указательных местоимений в английском и узбекском языках. Указательные местоимения играют важную роль в общении для точной идентификации человека, вещей и мест. В английском языке используются указательные местоимения «this», «that», «these» и «those», в то время как в узбекском языке используются формы «bu», «shu» и «u». В статье рассматриваются лингвистические структуры и синтаксические структуры обоих языков и представлены сходства и различия местоимений. На основе этого анализа выявлены общие и специфические особенности обоих языков, которые могут быть полезным источником знаний для изучающих иностранные языки.

Ключевые слова: указательные местоимения, английский язык, узбекский язык, сравнительный анализ, грамматика, синтаксис.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz va o'zbek tillarida ko'rsatish olmoshlarning tuzilishi, qo'llanishi va lingvistik vazifalarini qiyosiy o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Ko'rsatish olmoshlari odamlar, narsalar va joylarni to'g'ri aniqlash uchun aloqada muhim element bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ingliz tilida "this", "that", "these" va "those" ko'rsatish olmoshlari, o'zbek tilida esa "bu", "shu" va "u" shakllari qo'llaniladi. Maqolada ikkala tilning lingvistik tuzilmalari va olmoshlarning o'xshashliklari va farqlari ko'rsatiladi. Ushbu tahlil asosida ikkala tilning umumiy va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari aniqlanadi, bu chet tilini o'rganuvchilar uchun foydali bilim manbai bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'rsatish olmoshlari, ingliz tili, o'zbek tili, taqqoslash, grammatika, sintaksis.

Analyzing demonstrative pronouns in linguistics is essential for effective and accurate communication of information between participants in communication. The configuration of demonstrative pronouns, their structure, and the functions of each language have specific

grammatical and syntactic aspects. Demonstrative pronouns in English and Uzbek languages are served to convey such categories as closeness, distance, and abstraction in communication. In this article, this article will explore the structure and use of the demonstrative pronouns of the two languages and aim to recognize their differences and similarities. This comparative analysis establishes the foundation for a deeper understanding of grammatical categories in linguistics and illustrates the linguistic relationship between the two languages.

This, these, that, and those are used as demonstrative adjectives when they are followed by a noun and as pronouns when they are not followed by a noun.¹

Demonstrative pronouns are pronouns used to indicate a thing, a person: **u, bu, o'sha, ushbu, ana, mana, ana bu, mana bu.**²

He had seen lots of women behave **this** way around Willem³

U quloq **bu** qulog'ingiz bilan eshitib oling⁴

Although pronouns are used for the same purpose in English and Uzbek, their forms and the order of use differ, especially when expressing near and distance.

This and **these** are used: For people or things which are near us.⁵

Bu, shu, ushbu pronouns refer to things and persons in close proximity to the speaker.⁶

That and **those** are used: For people or things which are not near us. ⁷

The pronouns **u** and **o'sha** refer to things and persons far away from the speaker⁸

The collective amount of labor, real labor, that his trainmates had no doubt accomplished **that** day. ⁹

Hakimov...Kim bo'ladi **u** qushcha? ¹⁰

The demonstrative pronouns in English and Uzbek are grammatically different. In English, the plural and singular forms of demonstrative pronouns are defined separately: **this/that for singular, these/those for plural forms.**

In the Uzbek language, **the suffix "-lar"** is added to demonstrative pronouns to form the plural form: **bular, ular.**

Those people who still nursed it as the core of their identity came across as somehow childish.¹¹

Lekin yo'ldan **ularning** mashinasi o'tmay qolsa, xushyor bo'lish kerak. ¹²

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